

Hygrothermal Effects on CFRP Bonded Systems

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ABSTRACT

Non-symmetrical specimens composed of CFRP laminate and aluminum and bonded by different adhesives were exposed to severe hygrothermal conditions.

Variations in flexural displacement and moisture content of the CFRP were recorded during the exposure and compared with theoretical predictions. Results showed good agreement with the linear hygro-elastic behavior of a reference system composed of aluminum adherend and high-temperature adhesive, drying at 80°C being administered in all cases.

Specimens bonded by FM 73 adhesive exhibited a slowing down of the hygro-elastic process when exposed to hot-water, which is attributable to apparent residual "visco-plastic" deformations, which may be expected in this adhesive in such a stress environment.

The nearly full recovery of these and other specimens after total drying at 80°C is an indication of the prevailing visco-elastic mechanism of these adhesives and of the integrity of the bonded system.

INTRODUCTION

The mechanical behavior of bonded FRP/metal systems is highly complex due to the several counteracting mechanisms active simultaneously, all contributing to the internal stresses in, and the deformational behavior of, the three-phase bonded systems in different manners. Three external factors influencing stresses and deformations can be distinguished, namely: mechanical loading, thermal changes, and hygrometric conditions controlling moisture content and distribution within the adhesive, the matrix, and interfaces. In the course of the history of the bonded element thermal stresses are induced during cooling after the curing stage (1, 2). An increase in the moisture content and thermal fluctuations during the service life may lead to a reduction of the curing stresses through hygroelastic and thermoelastic mechanisms (3, 4, 5, 6). Hence, even under constant mechanical loading, stresses and deformations are changing with service-time in accordance with environmental conditions.

It must be emphasized that, as long as the internal stresses remain within the elastic range of the polymeric phases, all the above changes can be expected to be elastic and thus reversible when the original environmental conditions are resumed. Stress-relaxation, on the other hand, is a non-reversible mechanism which progresses with time and is also highly dependent on hygrothermal ambient conditions (7). It can be concluded that elastic stresses due to mechanical loading and thermoelasticity generally arise instantaneously and may combine to increase the chance of failure. Hygroelastic effects due to moisture penetration, on the other hand, are time-dependent mechanisms which may reduce the stress level and thus delay the failure process.

In previous studies it was found that a constant uniform distribution of in-plane stresses may be assumed throughout the adherends, except in very narrow regions close to the free edges (8). The assumption of plane stresses postulated in classical laminate theory (9, 10) is legitimate for a bonded system. On the other hand, interlaminar stresses at the adhesive layer which were found to be concentrated in a zone close to the free edges are significant and cannot be neglected.

Many analytical studies have been devoted to the computation of interlaminar stresses under both mechanical and thermal loading (11). In a recent work on a bonded CFRP/Aluminum system it was found that such stresses may exceed the elastic range of the material but that their distribution and peak values affect neither the adherend stresses nor the deformational behavior of the bonded system (12). Moreover, heating the system and keeping it at an elevated temperature for long periods does not result in measurable residual changes in the deformational fluctuations and stresses within the adherends after the system has cooled down to the original temperature. Since stress-relaxation of the polymeric adhesive at that temperature is very pronounced, it was concluded that the major effect was on the redistribution of stresses within the edge zone rather than on the integrated interlaminar forces and moments responsible for the deformation of the system and the stresses in the adherends.

One of the purposes of the present work is to extend the investigation to different bonded FRP/FRP systems, in which hygroelasticity follows the thermoelastic mechanism during curing.

The ambient conditions include the combined, hygrothermal, effects of moisture and temperature, which are expected to be reflected by the deformational changes due to fluctuations in adherend stresses and adhesive stress-relaxation with exposure-time.

The main objective of the present work, however, is an attempt to investigate, and distinguish between, the different mechanisms influencing the stresses and deformations of the bonded system, viz: thermoelastic, hygroelastic, and stress-relaxation.

MATERIAL COMPOSITION OF THE BONDED SPECIMENS

The specimens consisted of two different adherends bonded together by a thin adhesive layer in a non-symmetrical sequence (see Fig. 1). The adherends were aluminum alloy (2024/T3) and unidirectionally and cross-ply carbon-fiber-reinforced epoxy (CFRP) laminates.

The CFRP material, T300/5208, had a fiber content of about $V_f = 0.65$ by volume and had been cured at 175°C. The adhesives were: FM-73 for moderate temperatures (cured at 123°C) and FM-300 K for elevated temperatures (cured at 175°C), both produced by the Cyanamid Corporation.

Three types of specimens were prepared as described in Table 1.

Table 1 - Composition of the Bonded Specimens

Type of Specimen	Adherend 1		Adherend 2		Adhesive		T _{sf} (°C)
	lay-up	h ₁ (mm)	lay-up	h ₂ (mm)	lay-up	h _o (mm)	
CHA	CFRP 0°/90° 8 layers	1.10	Aluminum Alloy	1.0	FM 300 K	0.05	176
CHC	CFRP 0°/90° 8 layers	1.10	CFRP (90°) 16 layers	2.15	FM 300 K	0.10	176
CLC	CFRP 0°/90° 8 layers	1.10	CFRP (90°) 16 layers	2.15	FM 73	0.10	125

Specimens of the CHA series served as references, in which only small moisture effects on the adherend and non-relaxation of the adhesive are expected. Series CHC served for the study of the hygroelastic effects of the CFRP adherend on the bonded system. Series CLC served for the study of both hygroelastic effects on the adherends and visco-plastic relaxation behavior of the adhesive.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

After vacuum-oven-drying of the CFRP adherends, specimens were bonded and cured in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions. After curing the initial central deflection (curvature) was measured at 33°C by a special device shown in Fig. 2. All specimens were then heated up to the temperature level at which they became completely straightened out, by which means the stress-free-temperature (R_{sf}) of each specimen was determined (see Table 1).

After being weighed, the specimens were exposed to the following environmental history (see Table 2):

Table 2 - Sequence of the Environmental Exposures of the Bonded Specimens

Stage	Period (days)	Temperature	Humidity
I	3	80°C	Vacuum oven drying
II	4	33°C	45% R.H.
III	7	33°C	Water immersion
IV	14	80°C	Water immersion
V	9	80°C	Vacuum oven drying

During the environmental history, the specimens were transferred at short intervals to the measuring device in order to determine their deflection and to the scales for weighing, both at the reference temperature (33°C).

The basic elastic, thermoelastic, hygroelastic, and relaxation, characteristics of the CFRP adherends and adhesives were derived by conventional methods, as described in previous publications (13, 14, 15).

TEST RESULTS

Elastic Characteristics

The elastic properties of the unidirectional CFRP laminate and of the adhesive in the relevant hygrothermal conditions are given in Table 3. The effect of temperature on the shear moduli of the adhesives in dry and wet conditions is shown in Fig. 3, from which the glass-transition temperature (T_g) can be determined. From this figure it can be seen that T_g of FM 300 K is significantly higher than that of FM 73.

The depressant effect of moisture ($w = 1\%$), viz. = on the T_g is also shown, but only for FM 73.

Hygroelastic and Thermoelastic Characteristics

Typical weight changes (absorption) vs. time as a result of hot water-exposure for CFRP and adhesive are shown by the curves in Fig. 4. The respective typical curves of swelling deformation vs. exposure time are shown in Fig. 5. The higher diffusion rate in the cross-ply CFRP compared with its unidirectional reference is attributable to the thermoelastic stresses which were induced in the cross-ply laminate during curing.

Based on absorption and swelling data the almost linear relationship between hygroelastic deformation and moisture content was derived (Fig. 6) and the respective hygroelastic coefficients (HEC) were determined (Table 3).

Similarly, the thermoelastic coefficients (TEC) were determined from the linear relationship found to exist between thermoelastic strains and temperature difference, as shown in Fig. 7, and given in Table 3.

The unidirectional CFRP specimens (0°) were characterized by the well-known almost complete absence of longitudinal thermoelastic and hygroelastic deformations. This is, of course, attributed to the hygrothermal stability of the carbon fibers. On the other hand, the hygrothermoelastic characteristics of the transverse (90°) CRFP specimens were high, as can be expected of a matrix-controlled property.

Hygrothermoelastic deformation of the cross-plyed CRFP specimens is relatively low, as predicted by theory, and is closer to that of the longitudinal than to the transverse specimens.

Stress-Relaxation of the Adhesives

Stress relaxation of the FM 73 and FM 300 K adhesives was determined in the conventional manner, as described in refs. 14, 15.

In the previous works it was found that, in the linear viscoelastic range, relaxation and related characteristics are not affected by the loading mode. Furthermore, a relaxation master curve, valid for long periods, can be constructed on the basis of short term data obtained at different temperature levels.

The short-term relaxation curves for the two adhesives at different temperature levels are shown in Fig. 8.

The high relaxation rate of FM 73 ($T_g \approx 90^\circ\text{C}$) at temperatures above 70°C as against the much lower relaxation rate of FM 300 K adhesive ($T_g = 140^\circ\text{C}$), even at higher temperatures, is evident.

Hygrothermal Behavior of Bonded Specimens

Absorption Characteristics. - The curves of absorption vs. time for the different specimens are shown in Fig. 9.

A significant difference between the diffusion rates is evident: CHC has a slower absorption than CLC. This is attributable to the higher tensile stresses which exist in the external CFRP (90°C) layer in the CLC specimens during hot-water exposure.

The higher absorption rate of the CHA specimens during low-temperature exposure is attributable to the existence of tensile stresses in the $0/90^\circ$ CFRP layers, while the compressive stresses in the CFRP 90° layers of the CLC and CHC specimens during this exposure stage bring about a reduction in the rate of absorption. This finding, which is consistent with the higher absorption of the $0/90^\circ$ specimens as shown in Fig. 4, is further evidence of the stress-diffusion coupling effect which was found by different authors to exert a significant influence on the hygroelastic behavior of composite laminates (16, 17, 18, 19).

Adherend stresses were computed with the aid of the hygrothermoelastic composite laminate theory, assuming linear relationships between moisture content and temperature on the one hand and specimen deflection and adherend stresses on the other (see Fig. 10). That assumption is justified if the effect of inter-laminar stresses within the thin flexible adhesive on the overall deformational behavior of the bonded system is neglected (12).

Deformational Behavior. - The variations in the central deflection during the exposure period are shown in Fig. 11. Both CLC and CHC specimens exhibit a trend towards reduction in the initial deflection, which is slow in R.T. conditions, more pronounced in warm water, and highly accelerated in hot water exposure.

In both cases the specimens recover almost to the original deflection after total drying. This behavior is assumed to be due to the high capacity for swelling of the CFRP 90° adherend as shown by the pertinent theoretical curves. The deflection of the CHA specimens tends to increase due to the lower swelling tendency of its 0/90° adherend, which affects the bonded specimen in a direction opposite to that of the 90° CFRP adherend in the CHC and CLC specimens. Here also total recovery was found to occur on drying, and good agreement with theoretical expectations is evident during the whole exposure period.

DISCUSSION OF THE TEST RESULTS

A better understanding of several discrepancies in the behavior of the CLC, as compared with the CHC, specimens could be reached by plotting the experimental and the theoretical relationships between deflection and variations in moisture content during the absorption-desorption process (Fig. 12).

Some modes of behavior can be explained, as follows:

- (a) The slower variation in the curvature of the specimen during low-temperature exposure than would theoretically be expected is probably due to the fact that at this stage, the rate of absorption of the upper, cross-ply adherend is higher than that of the lower, U.D. adherend. This is due to the stress situation at this stage (see Fig. 9). In spite of the higher diffusion rate of the 0°/90° adherend, the central deflection does not increase, because the hygroelastic coefficient of the 0°/90° adherend is significantly lower than that of its CFRP 90° counterpart (see Fig. 6). Under hot-water exposure, the rate of hygroelastic deformation is accelerated due to the tensile stresses in the U.D. adherend, even beyond the theoretical rate.
- (b) In the case of CLC specimens, containing FM 73 adhesive, a significant deviation from the theoretical hygroelastic behavior was found, especially during the first several hours of hot-water exposure. This slowing down in the rate of change in residual deformation is attributable to the high relaxation rate and the visco-plastic characteristics of this adhesive prevailing in hot-water (see Fig. 8). Later, when the adhesive approaches its limit asymptotic relaxation, its behavior tends to conform to that predicted by theory.
- (c) In all specimens the experimental hygro-elastic relationship in drying is in good agreement with that predicted by theory. The reason for the almost total recovery from deformation, even in the case of the CLC relaxed system, is attributable to the special thermo-rheological characteristics of rubber-modified epoxy systems. Such copolymeric systems are characterized by complex rubber-elasticity and quasi-ductile modes of behavior, which manifest themselves in different loading conditions: while at temperatures below T_g they exhibit "yielding-ductile" and relaxation modes of behavior which seem to be residual, heating the material above a limit temperature releases all the frictional mechanisms which had been responsible for the residual deformation, and allows the specimen to recover its original shape. This mode of behavior was observed earlier in a different experiment, in which specimens were plastically deformed to up to 50% of the original dimensions and

fully recovered after appropriate heating.

(d) The behavior of the different specimens can be better understood by extrapolating their deformational variations under hot-water exposure, as shown in Fig. 13.

Here good agreement between hygroelastic theoretical expectation and experimental results was found for both CHC and CHA specimens, which are bonded with the high-temperature FM 300 K adhesive. On the other hand, in CLC specimens bonded with FM 73 the discrepancy between theory and experiment is obvious almost immediately upon hot-water exposure.

In that case the specimens, after curing, warped in the opposite direction to about twice their original curvature. As was shown in a previous analytical study (ref. 12) interlaminar stresses in such large deflections must be expected to exceed the "plastic-yield" limit of the adhesive. These interlaminar stresses and the resulting plastic strain in the adhesive seem to be responsible for the slow variation in residual deformation shown in Fig. 12. Theory appeared to point to a higher rate. The almost total recovery of the specimen's shape even in this case indicates that in spite of the strong non-linearity of the behavior, the integrity of the specimen's shape was preserved.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Exposure of non-symmetrical bonded CFRP and aluminum specimens to severe hydrothermal conditions resulted in variations in initial deflection strongly dependent on the absorption and desorption processes during the period of exposure.

The following conclusions could be drawn from experimental and hygroelastic analytical results:

(a) Adsorption in the CFRP adherend is dependent on the state of the stresses, which is itself a function of the hygroelastic deformational process involved. High flexural deformations due to hot-water exposure induced tensile stresses in external CFRP layers which in turn enhanced moisture diffusivity.

(b) The desorption-deflection relationship during drying coincides fairly well with the linear hygroelastic analytical relationship predicted for all the bonded systems involved.

(c) In specimens bonded by FM 73 adhesive, and under hot-water exposure at a temperature near its glass-transition point (T_g), a significant discrepancy in residual deformation was found to exist between experimental findings and analytical prediction. This is attributable to the visco-plastic-relaxation mode of behavior predominant in this adhesive at high levels of stress during hot-water exposure.

(d) In all cases, including that of apparent residual plastic deformation in the FM 73 adhesive, almost full recovery to the initial curved configuration was found after heating and total drying of the specimens. This points to the transient nature of the, apparently plastic, residual changes and indicates the predominant if delayed visco-elastic tendency of the bonded system to restore its initial configuration.

(e) Linear hygroelastic laminate theory seems to be applicable to bonded non-symmetrical CFRP systems as long as the non-linear visco-plastic processes do not predominate over a substantial portion of the bonded area.

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Table 3 - Elastic and Thermo-Hydroelastic Characteristics of the Material Constituents of the Bonded Systems

Material System	Test Conditions	Elastic Properties				Thermoelastic Properties $10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$		Hygroelastic Properties	
		E_{11} kg/mm ²	E_{22} kg/mm ²	G_{12} kg/mm ²	ν_{12}	α_1	α_2	β_1	β_2
CFRP 5208/T300	R.T. dry	15000	1000	600	0.27	-3.0	28.0	0	0.30
	70°C - moist	14000	900	450	0.27	0	30.0	0	0.47
Aluminum T3/2024		7300	7300	2740	0.33	22	20	0	0
Adhesive FM 73	R.T. dry	220	220	80	0.38	85	85	0.30	0.30
	70°C - moist	80	80	30	0.38	97	97	0.43	0.43
Adhesive FM 300 K	R.T. dry	245	245	88	0.38	77	77	0.40	0.40
	70°C - moist	180	180	65	0.38	84	84	0.50	0.50

REFERENCES

- 1 Sinha, P.K. and Reddy, M.N., "Thermal Analysis of Composite Bonded Joints," Fiber Science and Technology, 9, 1976, pp.153-159
- 2 Peretz, D., "Interlaminar Behavior of Bonded Bimaterial Systems," Composites, 1977, pp.153-156
- 3 Grimado, P.B., "Interlaminar Thermoelastic Stresses in Layered Beams," J. of Thermal Stresses, 1, 1978, pp.75-86
- 4 Chamis, C.C., Lark, R.F., and Sinclair, J.H., "Integrated Theory for Predicting the Hygrothermomechanical Response of Advanced Composite Structural Components," ASTM-STP-658, 1978, pp.160-192
- 5 Lee, B.L., Lewis, R.W., and Sacher, R.E., "Environmental Effects on the Properties of Glass Fiber/Epoxy Resin Composites," Technical Report of the Army Materials & Mechanics Research Center, 1978
- 6 Chung, T.J., and Prater, J.L., "A Constitutive Theory for Anisotropic Hygrothermoelasticity with Finite Element Applications," J. Thermal Stresses, 3, 1980, pp.435-452
- 7 Weitsman, Y., "Interfacial Stresses in Viscoelastic Adhesive Layers Due to Moisture Sorption," Int. J. Solids Struc., 15, 1979, pp.701-713
- 8 Ishai, O., and Gali, S., "Two-dimensional Interlaminar Stress Distribution within the Adhesive Layer of a Symmetrical Double Model," J. of Adhesion, 8, 201, 1977
- 9 Ashton, J.E., Halpin, J.C., and Petit, P.H., "Primer on Composite Materials Analysis," Technomic, 1969 (book)
- 10 Jones, R.M., "Mechanics of Composite Materials," ISE, 1970 (book)
- 11 Gali, S., and Ishai, O., "Interlaminar Stress Distribution within an Adhesive Layer in the Non-linear Range," J. of Adhesion, 9, 1978, pp.253-266
- 12 Yaniv, G., and Ishai, O., "Residual Thermal Stresses in Bonded Metal and FRP Systems," Composite Technology Review, 3, 4, 1981, pp.131-137
- 13 Gazit, S., and Ishai, O., "Hygroelastic behavior of GRP exposed to different relative humidity levels," Proc. of Conference on "Environmental degradation of engineering materials," Virginia Polytechnic Inst., Blacksburg, VA U.S.A., 1977, pp.383-392
- 14 Ishai, O., Moehlenpah, A.E., and Preis, A., "Yield and Failure of Glass-epoxy Composites," ASCE J. of Engineering Mechanics Div., 96, No. EM5, 1970, pp.739-752
- 15 Ishai, O., Gali, S., and Yaniv, G., "Durability of Structural Adhesively Bonded System," First Annual Report, Contract DAJA37-80-C-0303, U.S. Army European Office, June 1981
- 16 Fahmy, A.A., and Hurt, J.C., "Stress Dependence of Water Diffusion in Epoxy Resin," Polymer Composites, 1, No.2, 1980, pp.77-80
- 17 Whitney, J.M., and Browning, C.E., "Some Anomalies Associated with Moisture Diffusion in Epoxy Matrix Composite Materials," Advanced Composite Materials - Environmental Effects, ASTM STP-658, Vinson, J.R., Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, 1978, pp.43-60
- 18 Gilat, O., and Broutman, L.J., "Effect of an External Stress on Moisture Diffusion and Degradation in Graphite-Reinforced Epoxy Laminates," Advanced Composite Materials - Environmental Effects, ASTM STP-658, Vinson, J.R., Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, 1978, pp.61-83
- 19 Marom G., and Broutman, L.J., "Moisture in Epoxy Resin Composites," Journal of Adhesion, 12, 1981, pp.153-164

Fig. 1 - Typical lay-up of a bonded specimen.

Fig. 2 - Device for measuring variations in central flexural displacement of bonded specimens during hygrothermal exposure.

Fig. 3 - Shear modulus vs. temperature for FM 73 and FM 300 K adhesives.

Fig. 4 - Absorption vs. exposure time curves for CPSP and adhesive specimens (constituents of the bonded systems) exposed to hot water (70°C).

Fig. 5 - Swelling vs. exposure time for FM 300K and adhesive specimens, exposed to hot water (70°C).

Fig. 6 - Hygroelastic strains vs. moisture content for CFRP adherends and adhesive specimens.

Fig. 7 - Thermoelastic strains vs. temperature difference for CFRP adherends and adhesive specimens.

Fig. 8a - Tensile stress-relaxation curves for FM 300 K adhesive specimens at different temperature levels.

Fig. 8b - Tensile and compression stress-relaxation curves for dry and wet FM 73 adhesive specimens at different temperature levels.

Fig. 9 - Variations in moisture content vs. exposure time for the different bonded systems, related to the corresponding variations in CFRP adhered stresses.

Fig. 11 - Variations in central deflection at the reference temperature of bonded specimens with exposure time, under different hydrothermal conditions related to the respective hydroelastic predictions.

Fig. 10 - Theoretical hydroelastic relationship between central deflection and transverse stresses in the external unidirectional CFRP layer, for CHC and CLC bonded specimens.

Fig. 12 - Experimental vs. theoretical relationships between variations of central deflection of bonded specimens exposed to different hygrothermal conditions.

Fig. 13 - Variations in central deflection under hot-water exposure for the different bonded specimens, related to hydroelastic theoretical predictions.